

ISic3072

I.Sicily inscription 3072

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stucco

Object

painted wall

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Giovanni

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Catacomba di San Giovanni

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI331995

1. Παύλας ²⁷Πάλλας (Ferrua)²⁷.

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645424

PHI 331995

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 39.1024

Griesheimer, M. 1989. Quelques inscriptions chrétiennes de Sicile orientale. *Rivista di Archeologia Cristiana*. 65: 143-177. At 147 no.3 fig.3
undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.
Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 762 no.24

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3072. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4388069>